

Preparation and characterization of $ZrO_2/Y_2O_3/Al_2O_3$ -based microstructured multilayer sol-gel coatings

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Abstract

In this work several microstructured multilayer coatings with improved surface properties based on $ZrO_2/Y_2O_3/Al_2O_3$ systems were produced and characterized through a suitable combination of the sol-gel method with dip-coating, studying the influence of the Al_2O_3 load (0-20%) on the coating characteristics.

It was found that even at high alumina percentages, transparent, stable and suitable sols were obtained as a result of an optimized preparation method developed by our group. Sols synthesized allowed the preparation of high quality $ZrO_2/Y_2O_3/Al_2O_3$ -based microstructured multilayer sol-gel coatings. A noteworthy rise of Guglielmi and Zenezini's adimensional flow parameter (J) was observed by increasing the Al_2O_3 load, suggesting that the quantity of material deposited onto a substrate was also increased. This result also corroborates a slight increase of films thicknesses after heat treatments. In addition, an increase on the coatings porosity was revealed by increasing the alumina content that could probably affect the final properties of protective coatings.

Keywords: Thin layers, protective coatings, ceramic materials, dip-coating, zirconia (zirconium oxide), Al_2O_3 .

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1. INTRODUCTION

In many technological applications, constituent metallic materials can usually operate under extreme conditions (high temperatures, high pressures, chemically aggressive environments, etc.) which in turn can result in their early degradation. Many efforts are being made to design new materials that can deal and resist these conditions. Surface materials protection via advanced ceramic coatings represents an excellent alternative for metal substrates [1]. In fact, ceramics coatings have shown interesting physicochemical properties as well as an excellent stability and stiffness at high temperatures, high electrical resistivity, great corrosion and oxidation resistance [2], chemical inertness and acceptable wear resistance [3]. In this way, the study and development of new coating techniques represent a very timing research area. Particularly, over the last two decades, zirconia (ZrO_2)-based coatings have attracted the attention of many researchers mainly due to their important number and interesting technological applications [4-5].

Sol-gel coating technique is one of the most interesting alternatives for obtaining metallic oxide thin layers [6]. In fact, an important number of papers related to the versability and simplicity of this technique can be found in the literature [7-10]. Regarding other common techniques, sol-gel coating has shown several important advantages such as low-temperaure processing, chemical composition accurate control, excellent adhesion of coatings on different substrates, etc. [11]. Likewise, dip-coating is a well known coating process [12] which has also several and interesting advantages such as the possibility of coating large surfaces, the control of both the homogeneity and uniformity of the coatings, the simplicity of the equipment, and the low cost [13]. This technique is usually carried out by several successive stages: immersion, started-up under controlled speed, deposition and drainage, and evaporation. In this work, sol-gel coating

1 technique using dip-coating as deposition process has been employed for the preparation
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3 of zirconia (ZrO_2)-based coatings.
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6 Sol-gel coatings yields are markedly reliant on their structural quality. Usually,
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8 the presence of cracks and pores in coatings reduces dramatically their mechanical
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10 properties, and therefore, their protection effectiveness [14]. Consequently, the
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12 densification degree of coatings should be controlled on all the different stages of the
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14 process. Conversely, the presence of some porosity could improve thermal insulation
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16 which is usually important in several applications [15]. Moreover, film thickness control
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18 is also an important characteristic due to its technological importance. It is known that
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20 this parameter usually depends on both the sol-gel solution properties (density, viscosity,
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22 etc.) and the deposition process itself (start-up speed) [16]. Thus, the knowledge of the
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24 interaction and relationships between these variables becomes necessary in order to reach
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26 coatings with a specific thickness. In contrast, it is known that denser coatings usually
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28 improve the chemical, thermal and mechanical protection of the substrate [17]. Also,
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30 structural film quality and coating thickness (d) are sometimes irreconcilable; generally,
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32 there is a certain limit value for the film thickness from which cracks should appear
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34 resulting in a decrease of the coating effectiveness. As a consequence, the maximum
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36 coating thickness (d_1) is usually considered as the maximum thickness free of cracks that
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38 can be obtained in a single deposition process (monolayer coating). Nevertheless, it is
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40 possible to obtain coatings free of cracks with higher thickness than d_1 by means of
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42 multilayer coatings and taking into account the ratio between d and d_1 . This might be a
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44 worthy solution, especially if the highest possible thickness in each layer can be achieved
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46 by means of a simple process and with reducing the costs.
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1 During multilayer coatings preparation, it should be recommendable to determine
2 previously the maximum coating thickness, d_i , as well as the optimal experimental
3 conditions which are necessary to obtain d_i in a single deposition step [18-23]. Thus, it
4 could be possible to assure not only that every layer shows no cracks, but also the
5 optimization of the multilayer coating process.
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8 With these premises, the main objective of this work was the design, preparation
9 and characterization of ZrO_2 - Y_2O_3 - Al_2O_3 -based microstructured multilayer *sol-gel*
10 coatings. Particularly, the influence of Al_2O_3 percentage in precursor solutions on
11 thickness, porosity and microstructure (surface morphology) of the multilayer coatings
12 were investigated by spectrophotometric determination, reflected light optical microscopy
13 and scanning electron microscopy, and glow discharge optical emission spectroscopy. To
14 the best of the authors' known, the effect of this variable on the properties of these
15 materials has not been studied before.
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32 **2. MATERIALS AND METHODS**

33 **2.1 Substrate materials**

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2.2 Substrate coating

2.2.1 Preparation and characterization of stable sols

According to the procedure reported previously [6], a 3 mol% yttria-stabilized zirconia (3YSZ) sol was prepared mixing a solution containing zirconium n-propoxide (70%)/1-propanol (99%)/H₂O/HNO₃ (70%) with a molar ratio 1/15/6/1 with an yttrium acetate/2-propanol/H₂O/HNO₃ solution with a molar ratio of 1/15/6/1. The solution pH, measure by paper indicator (Acilit, Merck) was approximately 0.5. Viscosity and passing time values of the 3YSZ solution at different temperatures have already been reported elsewhere [7-14]. The results obtained showed that a temperature of 25 °C allowed a suitable behaviour of the solution as thin film enabling an accurate deposition.

Al₂O₃ sol was prepared by mixing aluminium tri-sec-butoxide with 1-propanol, followed by adding HNO₃ as catalyst. Molar ratio aluminium tri-sec-butoxide (97%)/1-propanol (99%)/H₂O/HNO₃ (70%) was equal to 1/15/6/1. The alumina sol was added into the 3YSZ sol under continuous stirring for 1 h to prepare 3YSZ-Al₂O₃(5wt.%) and 3YSZ-Al₂O₃ (20 wt.%) coating solutions. The pH of the solutions was approximately 0.5.

3YSZ, 3YSZ-Al₂O₃ (0.5wt.%) and 3YSZ-Al₂O₃ (20 wt.%) sols were characterized by measuring their density and viscosity at room temperature, using a Gay-Lussac pycnometer for liquids of 10 ml and an Ostwald modified type capillary viscometer, respectively (see Table 1). Sols prepared, as expected, were stable, clear and fairly transparent [24-32].

Table 1. Characteristics of prepared sols at 25 °C

Sols nomenclature	Density (g/cm ³)	Viscosity, η (cP)
3YSZ	0.894	5.1
3YSZ-Al ₂ O ₃ (5wt.%)	0.881	5.7
3YSZ-Al ₂ O ₃ (20 wt.%)	0.887	5.3

2.2.2 Coating and sintering

The prepared sols were deposited on the substrates at room temperature by dip-coating by means of an electromechanical testing machine HOYTON HM-20D using different withdrawal speeds (4-12 cm/min). Finally, coated substrates were dried at 100 °C for 1 h in air at ambient pressure. The dried coated substrates were annealed (sintered) at different temperatures ranging from 500 °C to 700 °C, depending on the substrate employed, using a quartz-tube furnace with a heating-cooling rate of 3°C/min and soaking time of 2 h under air atmosphere. The procedure followed for obtaining multilayer coating films involved the repetition of the above-mentioned consecutive stages between 3 and 5 times.

2.2.3 Film characterization

A standard Spectronic Helios Alpha UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific) was used over the spectral range of 200-1000 nm to analyse the ZrO₂/Y₂O₃/Al₂O₃-based monolayer and multilayers films coated on transparent substrates. This technique allowed the determination of the refractive index and transmittance curves of the different coatings. The porosity of coatings and thickness reached using different withdrawal speeds were determined by applying the Swanepoel's method [31] to the transmittance data as described in previous works [33-35].

1 The chemical composition depth profiling of $\text{ZrO}_2/\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ -based monolayer
2 and multilayers films was performed using a glow discharge optical emission
3 spectrometer (LECO-SA 200) over the spectral range of 165-400 nm on coated and
4 uncoated stainless steel substrates.
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10 A Nikon® reflected light optical microscope (Epiphot 300) was used in order to
11 assess the structural quality and the check the presence of the possible fissures and cracks
12 on $\text{ZrO}_2/\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ -based monolayer and multilayers films.
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18 The microstructure of $\text{ZrO}_2/\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ -based monolayer and multilayers films
19 was followed by scanning electron microscopy (SEM/EDX) using a Quanta® 3D FEG
20 (FEI) microscope. This technique also allowed the determination of their thickness.
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27 **3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**

28 *3.1 Influence of annealing temperature and withdrawal speed on optical properties of* 29 *coatings* 30 31 32 33 34

35 Figures 1a-b show the transmittance curves of a three-layer $\text{ZrO}_2/\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ -
36 based film obtained from sol 3YSZ and coated on a soda-lime glass substrate employing
37 different withdrawal speeds (0-12 cm/min) and diferent annealing temperatures (20-500
38 °C), respectively. For the sake of comparison, the transmittance spectrum of the bare
39 substrate was also included. From Figure 1a, it can be appreciated that the difference
40 between *peaks* and *valleys* remained almost unchanged in all coatings. Nevertheless, their
41 position and number were clearly modified and the number of peaks increased with the
42 withdrawal rate (or thickness film [25-29]). In contrast, transmittance spectra plotted in
43 Figure 1b show that the difference between peaks and valleys increased by rising
44 maximum annealing temperature, possibly owing to the greater density of the coatings.
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Figure 1. Transmittance curves of a three-layer $ZrO_2/Y_2O_3/Al_2O_3$ -based film obtained from sol 3YSZ and coated on a soda-lime glass substrate employing: a) different withdrawal rates (0-12 cm/min) and heat-treated at 500 °C, and b) different annealing temperatures (20-500 °C) and withdrawal rate of 10 cm/min.

Figure 2 illustrates that the refractive index, n , of thermally treated coatings became rather elevated at higher temperatures. This suggests that the film density was enhanced for higher annealing temperatures [13,30].

However, it does not seem very suitable to increase the temperature or the treatment time to reduce porosity, increasing its density, especially if the substrate can be degraded.

Figure 2. Refractive index versus wavelength for a coating thermally treated at 500 °C.

3.2 Influence of annealing temperature and withdrawal speed on thickness and porosity of coatings

Figure 3 shows the porosity variation with the annealed temperature employed. Porosity values (P) were obtained from different equations dependent on the refractive index (n_p) and thickness film (e_p) [26-28], for coatings treated between 300 and 1100 °C. It was found that the equation used (eqn. 1) was very appropriate equation for P calculations over the whole range of temperatures used, as it coincides accurately with eqn. 2 [26]:

$$P = 100 \times (1 - e_t / e_p) \quad (1)$$

$$P = 100 * [1 - (n_p^2 - 1) / (n^2 - 1)] \quad (2)$$

Figure 3. Porosity versus annealing temperature

Table 2 shows a comparative study of porosity (P) and thickness (d) of all transparent substrates coated with both monolayer and two-layers coatings. From the results, it can be observed that there were almost no differences among layer porosities. Besides, soda-lime glass and sapphire did not lead to important differences in coatings thickness and the two-layer films deposited on the same substrate under different experimental conditions showed similar thicknesses. As can be noted from Table 3, experiments carried out using soda-lime glass and silica glass substrates revealed only differences in coatings thickness of around 6 nm.

Table 2. Porosity (P) and thickness (d) for a monolayer and a two-layer coatings using a withdrawal speed of 16 cm min⁻¹ and an annealed temperature of 500°C.

Substrate	Coefficient of linear thermal expansion, α ($^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1} \times 10^{-6}$) [1]	monolayer coating		two-layer coating	
		<i>P</i> (%)	<i>d</i> (nm)	<i>P</i> (%)	<i>d</i> (nm)
Soda-lime glass	9.0	24.5	184	23	182
Silica glass	0.8	24.5	176	23	174
Sapphire	8.8	24.5	185	23.5	183

Table 3. Porosity (P) and thickness (d) for a monolayer and a 2-layer coatings using a withdrawal speed of 14 cm min⁻¹ and an annealed temperature of 500°C.

Substrate	Coefficient of linear thermal expansion, α [1] ($^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1} \times 10^{-6}$)	monolayer coating		two-layer coating	
		<i>P</i> (%)	<i>d</i> (nm)	<i>P</i> (%)	<i>d</i> (nm)
Soda-lime glass	9.0	26	168	25	168
Silica glass	0.8	24	162	25	162

These results suggest that the slight layer thicknesses variations observed could be mainly attributed to the existing differences among the thermal expansion coefficients of substrates. Thus, substrates with higher thermal expansion coefficients favoured the highest thickness values (see Tables 2 and 3), mainly, as a direct consequence of the important compressive stresses originated during the cooling stage.

3.3 Thickness and porosity of coatings deposited on stainless steel substrates

The film thicknesses obtained from the different sols (3YSZ, 3YSZ-Al₂O₃ (0.5wt.%) and 3YSZ-Al₂O₃ (20 wt.%)) coated on stainless steel substrates were determined by the Swanepoel method [29] under several withdrawal rates (4-12 cm/min). From the experimental values showed in Figure 4, it can be observed that films thickness values remarkably increased for higher withdrawal rates of the deposition process. Furthermore, it is worth noting that the slope of the curve increased with the alumina content in sols. This might suggest that increasing the velocity is enough to make the coatings thicker; however, there is a critical velocity at which the materials cracking occurs. This critical velocity was measured experimentally by coating the sols on the soda-lime glass substrates at different withdrawal rates. As soon as the sols were thermally treated at 500 °C, those possible cracks were identified by a metallographic microscope. Critical withdrawal rate, v_{max} , was considered as that at which coatings started to crack. However, it is known that this parameter is also dependent on the thermal treatment [6]. Thus, the critical withdrawal rate, v_{max} , of each solution as well as the viscosity, η , were considered, as both are assumed to be dependent on time [6]. As a result, the parameter that could better determine the maximum withdrawal rate for each solution was: $v_{max} \cdot \eta$ (see Table 4).

Figure 4. Thickness of coatings thermally treated at 500 °C for 2 hours versus withdrawal speed. Coatings: 3YSZ (green dots), 3YSZ-Al₂O₃ (5wt.%) (magenta dots) and 3YSZ-Al₂O₃ (20 wt.%) (purple dots).

Table 4. $v_{max} \cdot \eta$ for the different sols

Solution	Viscosity, η (cP)	v_{max} (cm/min)	$v_{max} \cdot \eta$ (cm.cP/min)
3YSZ	5.1	17.0	85
3YSZ-Al ₂ O ₃ (5wt.%)	5.7	12.3	70
3YSZ-Al ₂ O ₃ (20 wt.%)	5.3	11.3	60

Figure 5 shows the coating porosity values versus withdrawal rates of each solution. As can be observed, the porosity remained steady and almost it was not influenced by the withdrawal rate employed. However, it was noted that the increase of the percentage of alumina in the solutions increased significantly the porosity of the obtained coatings.

Figure 5. Porosity of coatings thermally treated at 500 °C for 2 hours versus withdrawal rate. Coatings: 3YSZ (green dots), 3YSZ-Al₂O₃ (5wt.%) (magenta dots) and 3YSZ-Al₂O₃ (20 wt.%) (purple dots).

The thickness and porosity of the different single layers in multilayer coatings resulted rather similar in all the cases studied. This suggests that the successive thermal treatments that were applied to inner layers did not affect significantly the general characteristics relative to thickness and porosity.

3.4. Analysis of the dimensionless flow parameter, J . Critical Thickness

The dimensionless flow parameter (J) of Guglielmi and Zenezini equation [24] can relate the film thickness, e_p , with the physicochemical properties of the solutions and the withdrawal rate by the following equation:

$$t_p = J \cdot \frac{C_p \cdot 10^{-3}}{\rho_p} \cdot \left(\frac{\eta \cdot v}{\rho_s \cdot g} \right)^{1/2}$$

1 where η and ρ_s are the viscosity (Pa·s) and the density (g/cm³) of the solution,
 2 respectively, v is the substrate withdrawal rate (cm/min), g is the acceleration due to
 3 gravity (980 cm/ss), J is the dimensionless flow parameter, ρ_p is the density of the heat-
 4 treated film (g/cm³), and C_p is the solute concentration in the solution (in grams of final
 5 oxide per litre) [30,31]. Figures 6a-c show the liquid film thickness (t) versus the
 6 characteristic thickness (t_0) plots corresponding to films deposited from 3YSZ, 3YSZ-
 7 Al₂O₃ (5wt.%), and 3YSZ-Al₂O₃ (20 wt.%) solutions. The J values were obtained from
 8 the slope of the plot.
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52 **Figure 6.** Liquid film thickness (t) vs. characteristic thickness (t_0) for films deposited
 53 from (a) 3YSZ, (b) 3YSZ-Al₂O₃ (5wt.%), and (c) 3YSZ-Al₂O₃ (20 wt.%) solutions. The
 54 lines represent the best-fit slope ($J = t / t_0$) through the data points.
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1 From the values of the parameter J inserted in Figures 6a-c, it can be noted that J
2 increased for greater alumina loads in sols, which is consistent with an increment of the
3 quantity of material deposited on the coating. Indeed, although J is an indicator of the
4 amount of coated material, the final thickness reached in the deposition processes is
5 affected by multiple factors, including the nature and quantity of solvent, the viscosity
6 and pH of the solution, stresses in the films, etc.

17 3.5 Coatings surface characterization

21 SEM micrographs in Figure 7 show the cross section of a five-layer film coated
22 on a stainless steel substrate at different magnifications. From this figure, the thickness of
23 the film was estimated to be around 1 μm . Also, the following layers were identified from
24 bottom to top of the pictures: stainless steel substrate (point 1), five-layer 3YSZ- Al_2O_3
25 (5wt.%) film (points 2 and 3), mixtures of resin and steel originated during the polishing
26 stage (points 7-9), and the epoxy resin used for embedding the sample (point 10). EDX
27 spectrum in Figure 8 confirmed the layer distributions mentioned.

54 **Figure 7.** SEM micrographs (cross sections) of a five-layer 3YSZ- Al_2O_3 (5wt.%) film
55 deposited on a stainless steel substrate and cured at 500 $^{\circ}\text{C}$.
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Figure 8. Energy dispersion X ray (EDX) pattern of point 4 in the sample showed in Figure 7(b).

3.6 Composition and thickness of coatings

The chemical composition depth profiling of different coatings was performed using a glow discharge optical emission spectrometer (GD-OES) over the spectral range of 165-400 nm on coated and uncoated stainless steel substrates. Figures 9 a-c show GD-OES depth profiles of Zr, Cr, Fe, O, Ni, C and Al for $ZrO_2/Y_2O_3/Al_2O_3$ -based films deposited on stainless steel with five layers obtained from 3YSZ, 3YSZ- Al_2O_3 (5wt.%), and 3YSZ- Al_2O_3 (20 wt.%) sols and heated at 700 °C. The average film thickness was around 1 μm .

Figure 9. Detailed view of the GD-OES depth profiles for Zr, C, Fe, Cr, O, Ni and Al of $\text{ZrO}_2/\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ -based films obtained from sols (a) 3YSZ, (b) 3YSZ- Al_2O_3 (5wt.%), and (c) 3YSZ- Al_2O_3 (20 wt.%) deposited on stainless steel substrates and heat-treated at 700 °C.

Results from Figure 9a evidenced that zirconium and oxygen profiles appeared nearly overlapped at the annealing temperature of 700 °C. This result may confirm that, at this stage, ZrO_2 was already developed. In fact, these two elements appeared nearly in similar ZrO_2 stoichiometry percentages (i.e. Zr: 75 wt.% and O: 25wt.%) [32-37]. Profiles in Figures 9b and 9c illustrate that aluminium profiles were also overlapped. Specifically,

1 the percentage by weight of aluminium was approximately 2.5 wt.% (see Figure 9b) and
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3 10 wt.% (see Figure 9c), respectively, confirming the ZrO_2 and Al_2O_3 compounds
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5 stoichiometry in the films. It is worth to note that aluminum appeared virtually constant
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7 throughout the whole coating and no diffusion to the outside was observed. Carbon
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9 content, which may indicate the presence of organic waste in the sample, was almost
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11 negligible at 700 °C. Also, small amounts of other elements such crome, nickel and iron
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13 can be onserved at the interfase. This may be due to the probable diffusion of these
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15 elements from the stainless steel substrate to the coating. This fact can sometimes limit
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17 the maximum annealing temperature employed since it may lead to the degradation and
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19 drop of mechanical properties [1, 37, 38].
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27 CONCLUSIONS

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29 From the results obtained and discussed in the present study the following conclusions
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31 can be obtained:
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- 35 - Several high quality microstructured multilayer *sol-gel* coatings based on
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37 $ZrO_2/Y_2O_3/Al_2O_3$ systems have been sucessfully developed and characterized.
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39 The increase of the percentage of aluminum oxide in sols has not inhibited the
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41 preparation of suitable, transparent and homogeneous sols.
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- 44 - Increasing the alumina load in the solution results in a significant increase of the
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46 film thickness, as suggested dimensionless flow parameter, J , results. In addition,
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48 a slight increase in the final thickness of the films after thermal treatment was also
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- The presence of alumina in the solutions, as well its quantity increased significantly the porosity of the final coatings obtained. This fact could affect significantly the mechanical properties of coatings.
- Both monolayer or multilayer coatings deposited on the same type of substrates showed similar thickness and porosity under the same experimental conditions (i.e. withdrawal speed and annealing temperature).
- Crystalline nature and microstructure of substrates influenced slightly the thickness of films, but not their porosity.

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